

Workflow Architecture to Optimize Processes in an Oncology Clinic

Arquitetura Workflow para Otimizar Processos em Clínica Oncológica
Arquitectura de Workflow para Optimizar Procesos en una Clínica Oncológica

Igor Amaral Martins¹

igor.martins5@fatec.sp.gov.br

Wilson Vendramel¹

Wilson.vendramel@fatec.sp.gov.br

1 - Fatec Zona Leste

Recebido
Received
Recibido

Dezembro, 2024
December, 2024
Diciembre, 2024

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado
Maio, 2025
May, 2025
Mayo, 2025

Publicado
Published
Publicado
Junho, 2025
June, 2025
Junio, 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.29327/2384439.3.3-6

São Paulo
v. 3 | n. 3
v. 3 | i. 3

e33352

Abril-Junho
April-June
Abril-Junio
2025

Abstract:

Efficient workflow management is crucial for oncology clinics, enabling them to deliver high-quality care and effective treatment. This paper proposes a solution based on a workflow architecture to optimize clinical processes in an oncology clinic, with a focus on operational efficiency. The proposal is based on documentary research and literature reviews of clinical requirements, as well as the definition of an adapted architecture, using modeling techniques to ensure scalability, security, and maintainability. Diagrams with UML and BPMN notations are presented as a foundation for future projects, aiming to unify and automate workflows. The results obtained cover the first two stages of the architectural lifecycle (requirements analysis and design). Although this proposal does not involve full implementation, it provides a robust framework for the future development of functional, cohesive, and maintainable software systems, with the need for practical validations.

Keywords: Workflow; BPMN; Architectural Views of Software; FURPS+.

Resumo:

A gestão eficiente dos fluxos de trabalho é essencial para clínicas de oncologia, visando garantir a qualidade do atendimento e a eficácia dos tratamentos. Este trabalho propõe uma solução baseada em arquitetura workflow para otimizar processos clínicos em uma clínica de oncologia, com foco na eficiência operacional. A proposta é fundamentada em pesquisas documentais e revisões bibliográficas de requisitos clínicos e na definição de uma arquitetura adaptada, utilizando técnicas de modelagem para garantir escalabilidade, segurança e manutenibilidade. Diagramas com notações UML e BPMN são apresentados como base para projetos futuros, visando a unificação e automação dos fluxos de trabalho. Os resultados obtidos cobrem as duas primeiras etapas do ciclo de vida arquitetural (análise de requisitos e design). Embora esta proposta não envolva a implementação completa, ela fornece uma estrutura robusta para o desenvolvimento futuro de sistemas de software funcionais, coesos e manuteníveis, com a necessidade de validações práticas.

Palavras-chave: Workflow; BPMN; Visões Arquiteturais de Software; FURPS+.

Resumen:

La gestión eficiente de los flujos de trabajo es esencial para las clínicas de oncología, con el objetivo de garantizar la calidad de la atención y la eficacia de los tratamientos. Este trabajo propone una solución basada en arquitectura de flujo de trabajo para optimizar los procesos clínicos en una clínica de oncología, con enfoque en la eficiencia operativa. La propuesta se basa en investigaciones documentales y

revisiones bibliográficas de requisitos clínicos, así como en la definición de una arquitectura adaptada, utilizando técnicas de modelado para garantizar escalabilidad, seguridad y mantenibilidad. Se presentan diagramas con notaciones UML y BPMN como base para proyectos futuros, con el objetivo de unificar y automatizar los flujos de trabajo. Los resultados obtenidos cubren las dos primeras etapas del ciclo de vida arquitectónico (análisis de requisitos y diseño). Aunque esta propuesta no implica una implementación completa, proporciona un marco robusto para el desarrollo futuro de sistemas de software funcionales, cohesivos y mantenibles, con la necesidad de validaciones prácticas.

Palabras clave: *Workflow; BPMN; Vistas arquitectónicas de software; FURPS+.*

1. INTRODUCTION

As pointed out by Chaudhry et al. (2006), Information Systems (IS) in the Healthcare Sector offer numerous advantages, including full access to patient data, error reduction, cost minimization, data security and improved patient care.

According to Gooch's (2011) studies, the application of workflow architecture in healthcare also contributes to patient safety and regulatory compliance. Activity traceability, audit trails, and consistent application of clinical protocols are fundamental elements of care.

In oncology clinics, efficient workflow management is crucial for ensuring the quality of care and the success of treatments offered to patients. Software based on workflow architecture emerges as a promising approach to optimize and improve clinical processes in this complex setting.

According to Winchester (1999), workflow architecture is a structure that allows the automation and management of workflows, defining the logical sequence of activities and the interaction between different systems and professionals.

Martin (2019) points out that it is common for programmers, faced with a new challenge, to embark on an implementation effort without prior planning, thereby highlighting the behavior of a solution at the detriment of its architecture. Consequently, this results in rigid, expensive, and difficult-to-maintain systems, thus compromising their longevity, which is the opposite of what is desired for software that stores vital information.

The proposal for software based on workflow architecture aims to enable the implementation of control and monitoring mechanisms, ensuring compliance with standards and process quality, in line with Sommerville's (2011) assertion about software architecture.

The overall objective of this work is to propose software based on a workflow architecture for an oncology clinic, with a focus on optimizing the treatment flow and patient follow-up. The study will identify the clinic's needs by analyzing the challenges and opportunities of applying this approach in the oncology setting. It is essential to note that this work does not encompass system implementation but instead focuses on the first two phases of the architectural lifecycle: Requirements Analysis and Architectural Design, including the proposal of an architectural project utilizing suitable technologies.

Ultimately, this work is justified by its contribution to streamlining clinical practices, providing a solid foundation for proposing technological solutions that optimize workflow management, enhance process efficiency, and promote more integrated and personalized patient care, thereby reflecting the evolution of the healthcare field with appropriate technological support.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

According to Pressman (2011), software architecture is the foundation of a system, encompassing its components, visible properties, and interactions. It encompasses the key design and organizational decisions that shape the system and is responsible for ensuring that it meets both functional and non-functional requirements. In the context of software architecture, workflow architecture is a specific approach that focuses on automating and managing workflows within the system, facilitating coordination between processes and improving efficiency.

To give a clearer view of software architecture, the following can be checked:

Would you try to build a house without a blueprint? You would not draw the blueprints starting with the house's plumbing layout, either. You should start with the big picture—the house itself—before worrying about the details. That is precisely what architectural design does—it provides an overview and ensures you understand it correctly (Pressman, 2011, pp. 387-388).

Software architecture is not just about creating diagrams; it encompasses much more than you might imagine, from identifying components, relationships, layers, architectural patterns, and architectural qualities to implementing and testing the software, ultimately generating benefits from its use.

Larman (2007) emphasizes the importance of software architecture as a fundamental element for a system's success. He highlights the benefits of proper architecture, including effective communication, reusability, maintainability, scalability, and testability, and encourages an iterative and flexible approach to architectural design, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1- Benefits of software architecture

Benefit	Definition
Understanding and communication	The architecture provides a clear visual representation of the system, which not only facilitates an understanding of the components and their interactions but also serves as a common language between the development team and <i>stakeholders</i> . This promotes more effective collaboration, ensuring that everyone involved has a shared understanding of the project objectives and system functionality, thereby reducing ambiguities and misunderstandings.
Reuse	Identifies reusable components, saving time and effort in development.
Maintainability	Good architecture facilitates system maintenance and evolution by allowing teams to quickly identify the source of problems and implement fixes or improvements. This is achieved through a modular structure that separates functionalities, simplifying the implementation of changes and the addition of new features. This flexibility is essential in a constantly changing technology environment, where user requirements and demands can evolve rapidly.
Scalability	Allows you to scale the system to handle increased load or new performance requirements.
Testability	Facilitates test creation, improving coverage and detection.

Source: Adapted from(Larman, 2007)

2.1 Workflow Architecture

According to Aalst (2004), a workflow is a formalized and automated

representation of a business process that defines the sequence of activities, control logic, and interactions between people, systems, and resources, to achieve a specific objective. It involves the coordination and efficient management of tasks, information, and resources involved in the process, ensuring the orderly and consistent execution of activities, based on predefined business rules and policies. Sommerville (2011) further emphasizes the importance of correctly modeling workflows, considering the different types of tasks, the sequencing of activities, the coordination between participants, and the integration with other systems. He emphasizes that the workflow architecture must be designed to support the specific demands of the business environment.

As Aalst (2004) points out, workflow architecture involves the automation, management, and coordination of business processes through information systems. It is based on a clear understanding of business processes and uses modeling techniques to represent them visually or textually. These models capture the structural and behavioral aspects of processes, defining the activities involved and their interactions, as suggested in Table 2.

Table 2 Workflow architecture concepts

Business process	A series of coordinated activities aimed at achieving a specific objective, forming the basis of <i>workflow architecture</i> .
Process modeling	Representation of processes using notations such as BPMN to capture structural and behavioral aspects.
<i>Workflow</i>	Automation and management of processes through systems, with a focus on designing flexible and efficient workflows.
Coordination and collaboration	Coordinates people, systems, and resources in processes, assigning tasks and facilitating interaction between participants.
Exception management	Addresses exceptions and deviations from the normal flow, with techniques such as dynamic routing and exception handling.
Monitoring and analysis	Provides mechanisms to monitor process execution and collect data for analysis and reporting.

Source: Adapted from (Aalst, 2004)

2.2 Architectural life cycle

The architectural life cycle refers to the process by which the architecture of a software system is conceived, designed, implemented, and evolved. According to Bass, Clements, and Kazman (2012), the architectural life cycle typically comprises several stages, as outlined in Table 3.

For Bass, Clements, and Kazman (2012), this is a continuous and iterative process, as the architecture must keep pace with changes in the environment, requirements, and technologies. It is essential to ensure robustness, flexibility, and adaptability of the *software system* over time.

Table 3- Life cycle stages and their definitions

Requirements analysis	Collects and analyzes RF and RNF, considering user needs and technical constraints.
Architectural <i>design</i>	Defines the structure of the system.
Implementation	Coding of system components based on architectural <i>design</i> and selected technologies.
Testing and validation	Functionality, performance, and security testing to ensure the system meets requirements.
Implementation and operation	Installation and configuration of the system in production, making it operational and available for use.
Evolution and maintenance	Adjustments and improvements to the architecture to meet new requirements and resolve identified problems.

Source: Adapted from(Bass, Clements e Kazman, 2012)

According to Kruchten (1995), the description of how *software systems work* is based on the use of multiple concurrent views. These views are used to present the system from various perspectives, including those of end-users, developers, and project managers. The 4+1 model consists of four main views: the logical view, which describes the system structure in terms of classes and objects; the development view, which focuses on the organization of code and *software components*; the process view, which addresses the system dynamics, including its interactions and workflows; and the physical view, which represents the infrastructure and the distribution of hardware components. The fifth view, called the **use case view** or "+1," illustrates the system architecture through scenarios that integrate the other views. Figure 1 presents an example of this model, which will be used throughout this work to guide the analysis and development of the proposed architecture.

Figure 1- 4+1 Model

Source: Adapted from(Kruchten, 1995)

3. METHOD

Given the context of oncology clinics and the need to improve the efficiency of clinical processes, this study aims to help organize and streamline patient treatment and follow-up processes, based on workflow architecture. Bibliographic and documentary research were conducted to support the

proposal.

3.1 Architectural life cycle

The case study involves an oncology clinic that requires a software application to enhance its workflow, including controlling patient arrivals, maintaining patient records, tracking consultations, health professionals, chemotherapy, and patient progress.

3.2 Architectural life cycle

The Architectural Lifecycle is a fundamental process that encompasses the phases of system development, from requirements identification to implementation and maintenance, as mentioned in section 2.2. In this work, the Requirements Analysis phase is essential for understanding the clinic's needs and serving as the basis for the proposal. To understand the clinic's needs and develop the proposal, two main approaches were adopted:

Bibliographic Review: A literature review was conducted on workflow management in oncology clinics and workflow architecture, providing a theoretical basis for the proposal.

Documentary Research: Research was carried out on *online articles*, selected to provide a more detailed understanding of the processes and demands of the clinics, namely (Tummers et al., 2021; Bulcão-Neto et al., 2022; Pufahl et al., 2022; De Ramón Fernández et al., 2020; Chaudhry et al., 2006).

After analyzing the case study, functional and non-functional requirements were identified. Non-functional requirements (NFRs) include testability, usability, interoperability, maintainability, scalability, security, and performance.

Table 4 describes the functional requirements (FR), which define the functionalities and actions the system must perform to meet operational needs. These requirements encompass managing registration data, displaying information, and controlling activities related to medical care and specific procedures.

Table 4- Functional Requirements (FR)

Code	Description
RF01	Maintain patient registration information.
RF02	View a schedule of appointments.
RF03	Confirm the patient's arrival.
RF04	Record registration data for queries and developments.
RF05	List the developments and registered patients.
RF06	View the progress of a specific patient.
RF07	Record chemotherapy procedures.
RF08	Request medication from the nursing station.
RF09	Maintain healthcare professional information.
RF10	Display the calendar with appointments and chemotherapy scheduled for the day.

Source: Authors (2024)

Next, Table 5 presents the **business rules (BRRs)**, which establish the policies and constraints that the system must follow to ensure the correct execution of

processes. These rules are essential to ensuring the system's alignment with the organization's operational standards and practices.

Table 5- Business Rules (NR)

Code	Description
RN01	Prohibits the registration of appointments on dates and times that are already occupied.
RN02	Prevents scheduling of new chemotherapy sessions at previously reserved times.
RN03	Removes the appointment from the calendar after 15 minutes of delay.
RN04	Limits the types of evolution allowed to: Medical or nursing complications.
RN05	Only health insurance plans are accepted as payment methods; other methods must be handled externally.

Source: Authors (2024)

3.3 Architectural life cycle

The Scenario View, proposed by Kruchten (1995), utilizes cases to demonstrate how the system meets both functional and non-functional requirements, thereby validating the architecture against user needs. This approach enables a more in-depth analysis of how different components interact under real-world usage conditions, ensuring that the designed architecture is robust and flexible enough to withstand changes. Scenarios also provide a practical, iterative view of the system's evolution, enabling stakeholders to visualize the system in operation and identify potential problems before they become critical. Furthermore, modeling with scenarios helps identify hidden requirements and prioritize essential functionality. Booch, Jacobson, and Rumbaugh (2005) state that the use case diagram is a graphical representation that details the interaction between users and the system, facilitating clear communication and a deeper understanding of the requirements. This visualization is essential for aligning the developers' vision with users' expectations and ensuring that all stakeholders share a clear understanding of the system's scope. In the case of this work, Figure 2 illustrates these interactions in a manner directly aligned with the objectives and requirements discussed, while also serving as a tool for continuous validation throughout the development lifecycle.

The study identified several use cases, each reflecting different functional and non-functional aspects of the system. However, only one of them will be presented in this paper due to space constraints. This specific case was chosen based on its relevance to the project objectives and its ability to illustrate the essential interactions between users and the system. The application of the FURPS (+) model followed the approach outlined by Eeles (2005) to ensure that all relevant aspects are considered during development. This structured approach will allow for a comprehensive assessment of the requirements, facilitating the identification of potential risks and opportunities for improvement. A detailed analysis is presented in Table 6, which provides a clear overview of the criteria considered and their relationship to the selected use case.

Figure 2- Use Case Diagram

Source: Authors (2024)

Although Table 6 identifies specific quality attributes as non-functional requirements, it is essential to note that other attributes were also identified in the architectural scenarios of the other use cases.

Table 6- Maintain Evolution Use Case

Use Case: CSU04: Maintain Evolution		
Description: The healthcare professional will be able to record an evolution in the system.		
Primary Actor: Doctor, Nurse		
Supporting Actor(s): N/A.		
Preconditions: Be logged into the system.		
Main Flow: 1. The Doctor enters the date the evaluation was performed, the type of evaluation (intercurrence, medical or nursing, according to RN04), the patient who received the evaluation, the health professional who performed the evaluation and the procedure that was performed. 2. The system checks whether there are doctors and patients with the data that was filled in. 3. The system confirms that the data already registered in the system exists and records the evolution.		
Alternative flow (3): Patient or doctor not found. a) The system cannot find a patient or doctor with the fields filled in. Return to step 1.		
Alternative flow (1): Consult developments or evolution. a) The Doctor will select the option to check progress. b) The system will provide the options to consult a list of evolutions or a specific evolution. c) The doctor may make changes or delete the progress that was opened or presented.		
Postconditions: Evolution has been recorded.		
Related Business Rules: RN04		
Architectural Scenarios	Architectural Requirement (according to FURPS+)	Architectural Requirement Description
For all use cases	Functionality/Security (Access Restriction)	The user needs to be authenticated by the system.
1. b)	Performance/Response Time	The system must display the result within 5 seconds at most.
For all use cases	Usability/Intuitive interface	The system must present organized fields and functions already pre-established for the user.

Source: Authors (2024)

3.4 Architectural life cycle

The Architectural Cycle is a structured set of steps that guides system development, with the *Architectural Design phase being one of the most critical*. This phase focuses on defining the system's structure, considering the interactions between the various components and user needs. During *Architectural design*, it is essential to create representations that visualize the *software's organization*, its functionalities, and their interrelationships, facilitating an understanding of the proposed architecture. Furthermore, these representations help identify potential integration issues and validate architectural decisions, ensuring that the solution meets both functional and non-functional requirements. Therefore, this phase is crucial to ensuring effective alignment between *stakeholder expectations* and system implementation.

3.4.1 Logical View

The Logical View, as proposed by Kruchten (1995), focuses on representing the system's components and the interactions between them. It details the business

interactions and dependencies. In Figure 4, the package diagram created for this work illustrates the system's layers, including business logic, information layer, and presentation layer. It represents the relationships between packages, highlighting how they can interact independently of the code, contributing to greater system flexibility and maintainability. This approach allows changes to one package to be made without directly affecting the others, promoting more robust and scalable architecture. Furthermore, the use of package diagrams facilitates the identification of integration and dependency points, which are crucial for implementing new features and identifying potential areas for improvement within the existing architecture. This clarity in the system structure is vital to ensuring the effectiveness of agile development and adapting to changing requirements throughout the software lifecycle.

3.4.3 Process View

The Process View, also part of Kruchten's 4+1 model (1995), addresses system dynamics, focusing on how processes interact and behave over time. This view utilizes activity diagrams and control flows to illustrate the flow of information and synchronization between various processes. It is essential for understanding system execution and ensuring that interactions occur as expected.

BPMN (*Business Process Model and Notation*) is a graphical notation designed to represent business processes clearly and concisely. It employs a range of symbols and conventions to represent key elements, including activities, events, flows, decisions, and interactions. This tool is widely used in process analysis, automation, and communication, allowing all stakeholders to have a shared and accurate view of the workflow. The notation includes components such as activities, events, sequence flows, decisions, *gateways*, *pools*, and *lanes*, as highlighted by Silver (2012). This structuring facilitates the documentation and understanding of processes, promoting efficiency and alignment among teams.

Two BPMN diagrams will be presented to illustrate the patient care process, which is essential for understanding the dynamics of the "Maintain Progress" use case. These diagrams provide a clear visual representation of the steps involved in care, enabling *stakeholders* to visualize how interactions occur in real-time. Figure 5 demonstrates the moment a registered patient arrives, highlighting the events and activities that mark the beginning of the process.

Figure 4- BPMN Diagram for the Maintain Evolution Use Case

Source: Authors (2024)

Upon arrival, the diagram in Figure 6 details the patient’s subprocess, addressing the activities required to determine the most appropriate type of procedure, considering the patient's specific needs and conditions. This approach ensures personalized and efficient care.

Figure 5- Forwarding subprocess

Source: Authors (2024)

3.4.4 Physical View

The Physical View, as proposed by Kruchten (1995), represents the system's infrastructure, detailing the arrangement of hardware components and their network configurations. This view is crucial for implementing and operating the system in real environments, providing a clear understanding of how physical elements connect and interact to support software functionality.

In the context of proposing a workflow-based solution for an oncology clinic, the web application architecture is structured in three layers: the Presentation Layer (Front-end), which handles the user interface; the Application Layer (Back-end), responsible for business logic; and the Data Layer (Database), where information is stored and managed. Selecting the appropriate tools and technologies for each layer is essential, considering integration with different languages and APIs, and will depend on the clinic's specific requirements and the availability of solutions.

Figure 7 illustrates the implementation of the physical part of the proposed architecture, highlighting the arrangement and interconnection of components in the different layers. This representation highlights the use of Camunda, an open-source platform for business process automation. According to Camunda (2024), this tool is effective in orchestrating workflow between layers, ensuring that patient treatment processes are coordinated in an integrated and efficient manner.

Figure 6- Web Architecture

Source: Authors (2024)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained so far refer to the first two stages of the architectural lifecycle: requirements analysis and architectural design. Requirements analysis was crucial for identifying the specific needs of the oncology clinic, encompassing both functional and non-functional requirements. The architectural design translated these needs into a coherent technical structure, defining the interactions between the system components in line with the quality guidelines presented by the authors. Nevertheless, it has not yet been possible to validate these results through practical implementation, which limits the analysis to a theoretical proposal.

The remaining four stages of the architectural lifecycle — implementation, testing, deployment, and maintenance — represent the expected outcomes essential to project completion. Implementation consists of coding the system components, where design decisions are put into practice. Subsequent testing, including unit, integration, system, and acceptance testing, will be crucial to validating the system's quality and ensuring that all requirements are met. This testing process will enable early identification of problems and adjustments and may even lead to iterations between stages of the architectural lifecycle, as needed.

The deployment phase will allow the system to be made available to end users. In contrast, the maintenance phase will ensure continuous improvement based

on user feedback and the clinic's changing needs. This iterative and collaborative approach ensures that the final solution is robust, scalable, and aligned with the clinic's needs, providing a streamlined workflow and effective patient follow-up.

In Figure 8, the 4+1 model is replicated, considering the elements present in this work that comprise each of the architectural views.

Figure 7- 4+1 models with application of the concepts used

Source: Authors (2024)

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The work focused on the first two stages of the architectural lifecycle, analyzing the requirements and proposing the architectural *design* for an oncology clinic. These stages were completed, resulting in a robust initial structure that meets the clinic's identified needs. The subsequent stages, involving implementation, testing, deployment, and maintenance, are planned as future deliverables. Full implementation and practical testing have not yet been completed, which limits the assessment of the system's final effectiveness. Regarding the objective of the work, it was achieved, demonstrating results that confirm this conclusion.

Although detailed and consistent architecture has been proposed, the lack of practical implementation means that its operational efficiency cannot yet be fully validated. To confirm the system's effectiveness, implementation must be completed, followed by a testing phase that validates the expected results.

Future work could focus on implementing the proposed system and conducting usability and performance tests to validate the *workflow's effectiveness* in practice. Furthermore, assessing the impact on service time and patient care quality should be part of a more in-depth post-implementation investigation.

Among the identified limitations, the need for integration with legacy electronic medical record systems stands out, which may necessitate significant adaptation efforts. Furthermore, the reliance on clinical staff training to operate the new architecture may pose a challenge in terms of technology adoption.

REFERENCES

- AALST, WVD **Workflow Management: Models, Methods, and Systems**. Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2004.
- BASS, L.; CLEMENTS, P.; KAZMAN, R. **Software Architecture in Practice**. 3rd ed. New Jersey: Pearson Education, 2012.
- BOOCH, G.; JACOBSON, G.; RUMBAUGH, J. **UML: User's Guide**. 2nd ed. Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, v. 1, 2005.
- BULCÃO-NETO, RF; NETO, VVG; MACEDO, AA **A reference architecture for healthcare systems with coded terminology support**. In: *Intermountain Engineering, Technology and Computing (IETC)*, 2022, Orem, UT, USA. Annals... 2022. p. 1-6. DOI: 10.1109/IETC54973.2022.9796889.
- CAMUNDA**. *Camunda Platform*. Available at: <https://camunda.com>. Accessed on: November 5, 2024.
- CHAUDHRY, B.; WANG, J.; WU, S.; MAGLIONE, M.; MOJICA, W.; ROTH, E.; MORTON, S.; SHEKELLE, P. **Systematic review: impact of health information technology on quality, efficiency, and costs of medical care**. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, vol. 144, no. 10, p. 742-752, 2006. DOI: 10.7326/0003-4819-144-10-200605160-00125.
- BY RAMÓN FERNÁNDEZ, A.; RUIZ FERNÁNDEZ, D.; SABUCO GARCÍA, Y. **Business process management for optimizing clinical processes: a systematic literature review**. *Health Informatics Journal*, vol. 26, no. 2, p. 1305-1320, 2020. DOI: 10.1177/1460458219877092.
- EELES, P. **Capturing architectural requirements**. *IBM Rational Developer Works*, 2001. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329760910_Capturing_Architectural_Requirements. Accessed on: June 20, 2023.
- GOOCH, P.; ROUDSARI, A. **Computerization of workflows, guidelines, and care pathways: a review of implementation challenges for process-oriented health information systems**. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association (JAMIA)*, vol. 18, no. 6, 2011. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/amiajnl-2010-000033>. Accessed on: October 16, 2024.
- JACOBSON, I. **Object-Oriented Software Engineering: A Use Case Driven Approach**. Boston: Addison-Wesley, 1992.
- KRUCHTEN, P. **The 4+1 View Model of Architecture**. *ResearchGate*, Nov. 1995. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220018231_The_41_View_Model_of_Architecture. Accessed on: October 24, 2024.
- LARMAN, C. **Using UML and Patterns**. 3rd ed. Porto Alegre: Bookman, 2007.
- MARTIN, RC **Clean Architecture - The Craftsman's Guide to Software Structure and Design**. 1st ed. Rio de Janeiro: Alta Books, 2019.
- PRESSMAN, R. **Software Engineering: A Professional Approach**. 9th ed. Porto Alegre: AMGH, 2011.
- PUFAHL, L.; ZERBATO, F.; WEBER, B.; WEBER, I. **BPMN in healthcare: Challenges and best practices**. *Information Systems*, vol. 107, 2022, p. 102013. DOI: 10.1016/j.is.2022.102013.
- SILVER, B. **BPMN 2.0 Handbook: Methods, Concepts, Case Studies and Standards**. 1st ed. Florida: Layna Fischer, 2012.
- SOMMERVILLE, I. **Software Engineering**. 9th ed. São Paulo: Person, 2011.
- TUMMERS, J.; TOBI, H.; CATAL, C. **Designing a reference architecture for health information systems**. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, v. 21, no. 210, 2021. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-021-01570-2>. Accessed on: October 27, 2024.

WINCHESTER. **Workflow patterns.** 1999. Available at:
<www.workflowpatterns.com/documentation/documents/TC-1011_term_glossary_v3.pdf>.
Accessed on: May 28, 2023.

"The content expressed in the work, as well as the copyright of figures and data, as well as its spelling and standards review, are the sole responsibility of the author(s)."

"The author(s) of the work declare(s) that during the preparation of the manuscript, the Artificial Intelligence (AI) tool(s)/service(s) [GPT4o, *Co-pilot and Consensus*] were used to [analyze and suggest possible grammatical corrections and assist in academic research]. After using this tool/service, the authors edited and revised the content as necessary and assume full responsibility for the content of the publication."